

Copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes mediated from an isolated oxime-based Schiff base ligand : Syntheses, structures, characterization, redox, thermal properties and BVS calculations

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Abstract : 3-(2-Amino-ethylimino)-butan-2-one oxime (LH), a hydrolysis-prone 1 : 1 Schiff base condensate of 2,3-butanedione monoxime and ethylenediamine (en), has been isolated in the solid state and thus has been characterized thoroughly. Reaction of LH with copper(II) acetate monohydrate in 2 : 1 molar proportion in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (THF) gives rise to novel [Cu(en)₂(CH₃COO)](PF₆) (1). The X-ray crystal structure reveals that 1 bears en, a hydrolyzed product of LH. However, 1 is unique in copper-en chemistry. On the contrary, similar reaction of LH with nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate fosters [Ni(LH)₂](PF₆)₂(THF)₂ (2). Thus under identical reaction conditions, LH as such stabilizes Ni^{II}. The X-ray crystal structure of 2 has also been determined. Both 1 and 2 have been characterized by C, H and N microanalyses, metal estimations, ESI-MS, FT-IR, UV-Vis spectra, molar electric conductivity measurements and room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements. The redox and thermal aspects of 1 and 2 have been studied. Bond-Valence Sum (BVS) model calculation was undertaken to reproduce the oxidation states of copper and nickel in 1 and 2 respectively.

Keywords : Oxime, crystal structure, redox behavior, thermal analysis, BVS calculation.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of oxime-based Schiff base ligands is really vast¹⁻⁴. The mode and ability of an oxime moiety to bind metal centers is varied owing to its ambidentate nature⁵⁻⁷. Again, the mode of coordination and/or stability of an oxime is greatly influenced by the presence of other ancillary group(s) present in an oxime-based ligand. Generally, a Schiff base oxime is susceptible to hydrolysis⁸. Even the hydrolyzed products obtained thereby may undergo subsequent transformation via possible pathways like rearrangement, cyclization etc. Consequently, the hydrolysis of such ligands facilitates to end up with novel organic, metallo-organic species^{9,10}. A novel hexadecanuclear mixed valence copper assembly has recently been shown to be stabilized by the unusual

mutual coordination arising out of a native Schiff base oxime ligand, its hydrolyzed fragment and the cyclised moiety of the hydrolyzed product¹¹. Hydrolysis of Schiff base oxime may lead to co-crystal formation¹². Thus this hydrolysis is meaningful in supramolecular chemistry as well.

Herein we wish to report the synthesis and isolation of a hydrolysis-prone Schiff base oxime ligand in the solid state. This has prompted us to characterize it thoroughly. Subsequent attempts to stabilize Cu^{II} with this ligand enabled us to isolate a novel monomeric Cu^{II} compound with 'CuN₄O' core that bears only the hydrolyzed ligand-fragment. Curiously for Ni^{II}, the ligand remains intact. Syntheses, characterization, redox and thermal aspects of both the compounds have been dealt with.

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

Analytical reagent grade chemicals were used as received. Tetrahydrofuran (specially dried, GR), ethyl acetate, *n*-hexane, ethylenediamine, aluminum oxide active (neutral activity I-II, according to Brockmann for column chromatography), molecular sieve (4 Å × 1.5 mm) and copper(II) acetate monohydrate were procured from Merck, India. Nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate was purchased from Loba Chemie, India. Ammonium hexafluorophosphate and 2,3-butanedione monoxime, 98% were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., USA. The melting points were determined using an electrothermal digital melting point apparatus (SUMSIM, India) and are uncorrected. C, H and N elemental analyses were performed by a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyzer. FT-IR spectra (KBr pellet) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer (Spectrum Two). The UV-Visible spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer. 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum (in DMSO-*d*₆ : reference, TMS) of **LH** was recorded on a Bruker DPX300 spectrometer. Solution conductivity measurements of **1** and **2** were done at room temperature on a Mettler Toledo FiveEasy Plus Conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of **1** and **2** were carried out at 300 K with a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a walker scientific L75FBAL magnet. Hg[Co(SCN)₄] was the calibrant and the data were corrected for diamagnetism using Pascal's constants. The positive ion ESI-mass spectra for **LH**, **1** and **2** were recorded on a Q-ToF Micromass spectrometer. Copper was estimated gravimetrically as CuSCN, while nickel as Ni(HDMG)₂. Cyclic voltammetric (CV) data were acquired on a Bioanalytical Systems Inc. Epsilon electrochemical workstation (Model : CV-50) on a C3 cell stand at 298 K. The measurements were carried out with a three-electrode assembly comprising a glassy carbon (GC) working electrode, a platinum-wire counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Thermal analyses (TGA/DTA) were performed under a dynamic nitrogen atmosphere (20.00 mL/min) on a Perkin-Elmer instrument (Model : Pyris Diamond TG/DTA).

Preparation of 3-(2-amino-ethylimino)-butan-2-one oxime (**LH**) :

0.404 g (4 mmol) of 2,3-butanedione monoxime was dissolved in 30 mL of dry THF to get a colorless solution. Then 0.26 mL (4 mmol) of en was added dropwise with constant stirring to the monoxime solution. The result-

ing colorless solution was heated under reflux for 3 h maintaining an anhydrous condition using pre-activated molecular sieves. The light yellow solution obtained thereby was vacuum evaporated to get a yellow viscous oil. This oil on standing in a vacuum desiccator overnight sets into a white mass. This mass was washed thoroughly with diethyl ether and was dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl₂. This crude ligand was purified by column chromatography in neutral alumina medium using ethyl acetate, *n*-hexane (2 : 1) mixed solvent as an eluting agent.

Yield : 0.272 g (48%), m.p. 126–128 °C, C₆H₁₃N₃O (143.18) : Anal. Calcd. for C₆H₁₃N₃O : C, 50.33; H, 9.15; N, 29.35%; Found : C, 50.14; H, 8.25; N, 29.84%; FT-IR (KBr) ν (cm⁻¹) : 3150(vb) [ν (O-H) of oxime], 3013(b), 2859(vb) [ν (NH₂)], 1609(s) [ν (C=N)], 1471(m) [ν (C=N) of oxime], 1127(m) [ν (N-O)], 1066(s) [ν (C-N)] and 996(s) [ν (C-C)]; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, TMS) δ (ppm) : 11.43 (1H, s, hydrogen of -OH group attached to oxime moiety), 3.69 (2H, s, amine protons), 2.78 (2H, s, methyl protons close to amine), 2.66 (2H, s, methyl protons close to imine N), 2.01 (3H, s, methyl protons near to -C=N group), 1.90 (3H, s, methyl protons close to oxime moiety); UV-Vis (CH₃CN) : λ_{\max} (nm) (ϵ_{\max} [M⁻¹ cm⁻¹]) = 223 (2.448 × 10³); ESI-MS (positive ion mode in CH₃OH) (*m/z*) : 145.06 (Calcd. 144.19) for [LH+H⁺] (100%).

Preparation of [Cu(en)₂(CH₃COO)](PF₆) (**1**) :

A 10 mL colorless solution of 0.029 g (0.2 mmol) of **LH** in dry THF was prepared by refluxing in anhydrous condition for 30 min. 0.02 g (0.1 mmol) of copper(II) acetate monohydrate was dissolved in 10 mL of dry THF on heating. The metal solution was added to the ligand solution dropwise with stirring at room temperature. A green solution was obtained thereby. The stirring was continued for 3 h. The color of the solution gradually changed to dark green. Then 0.024 g (0.15 mmol) of NH₄PF₆ dissolved in 10 mL of dry THF was added dropwise to the reaction mixture. The color of the solution immediately changed to brown. The stirring was continued for another 30 min. The solution obtained thereby was kept in a refrigerator for slow evaporation. After 4 days, blue needle shaped shining single crystals were obtained. It was washed thoroughly with diethyl ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl₂. Some of the blue crystals were fit for X-ray structure determination.

Bandyopadhyay : Copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes mediated from an isolated oxime-based *etc.*

Yield : 0.019 g (49%), m.p. 214 °C; $C_6H_{19}N_4O_2CuPF_6$ (387.76) : Anal. Calcd. for $C_6H_{19}CuN_4O_2PF_6$: C, 18.57; H, 4.94; N, 14.45; Cu, 16.39% : Found : C, 18.78; H, 4.80; N, 13.61; Cu, 15.95%; FT-IR (KBr) : ν (cm^{-1}) : 3378(b), 3316(b) and 3224(b) [$\nu(NH_2)$], 1581(m) [$\nu(C=O)$ of acetate], 1402(w) [$\nu(C-O)$ of acetate], 831(s) and 556(s) [$\nu(P-F)$]; UV-Vis (CH_3CN) : λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ_{max} [$M^{-1} cm^{-1}$]) = 610 nm (6.729×10^4), 229 nm (6.389×10^3); ESI-MS (positive ion mode in CH_3CN) (m/z) : 122.89 (Calcd. 122.02) for $[Cu^{63}(CH_3COO)]^+$ (100%), 124.91 (Calcd. 124.02) for $[Cu^{65}(CH_3COO)]^+$ (73.62%), 163.93 (Calcd. 164.56) for $[Cu^{63}(en)_2(PF_6)+H^+]^{+2}$ (71.78%), 165.94 (Calcd. 166.56) for $[Cu^{65}(en)_2(PF_6)+H^+]^{+2}$ (34.97%), 181.96 (Calcd. 182.09) for $[Cu^{63}(en)(CH_3COO)]^+$ (56.44%), 183.98 (Calcd. 184.09) for $[Cu^{65}(en)(CH_3COO)]^+$ (29.44%), 327.89 (Calcd. 328.09) for $[Cu^{63}(en)_2(PF_6)]^+$ (19.63%) and 329.92 (Calcd. 330.09) for $[Cu^{65}(en)_2(PF_6)]^+$ (8.59%); Λ_M (acetonitrile) : 114.058 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ (1 : 1 electrolyte); μ_{eff}/μ_B : 1.92 at 300 K.

Preparation of $[Ni(LH)_2](PF_6)_2 \cdot (THF)_2$ (**2**) :

0.029 g (0.2 mmol) of **LH** was dissolved in 10 mL of dry THF by refluxing in an anhydrous condition for 30 min to give rise a colorless solution. Then 0.025 g (0.1 mmol) of Ni^{II} acetate tetrahydrate was dissolved in 10 mL of dry THF by heating. The metal solution was added to the ligand solution dropwise with stirring at room temperature. A deep reddish green solution was obtained thereby. The stirring was continued for 3 h. Then 0.024 g (0.15 mmol) of NH_4PF_6 dissolved in 10 mL of dry THF was added dropwise to the reaction mixture. The color of the solution immediately changed to deep red. The stirring was continued for another 30 min. The solution obtained thereby was kept in a refrigerator for slow evaporation. After 7 days, brown block-shaped shining air-stable single crystals were obtained. It was washed thoroughly with diethyl ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$. Some of the brown crystals were fit for X-ray structure determination.

Yield : 0.031 g (40%), m.p. > 240 °C; $C_{20}H_{42}N_6O_4NiP_2F_{12}$ (779.25) : Anal. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{42}NiN_6O_4P_2F_{12}$: C, 30.82; H, 5.43; N, 10.78; Ni, 7.53%; Found : C, 30.67; H, 5.74; N, 11.41; Ni, 7.82%;

FT-IR (KBr) : ν (cm^{-1}) : 3379(vb) [$\nu(O-H)$ of oxime], 3330(vb) and 3154(vb) [$\nu(NH_2)$], 1598(m) [$\nu(C=N)$], 1436(m) [$\nu(C=N)$ of oxime], 1048(s) [$\nu(C-C)$], 837(s) and 555(s) [$\nu(P-F)$]; UV-Vis (DMSO) : λ_{max} (nm) (ϵ_{max} [$M^{-1} cm^{-1}$]) = 542 (2.060×10^2), 419 (6.552×10^2), 310 (1.197×10^3); ESI-MS (positive ion mode in MeOH) (m/z) : 343.05 (Calcd. 343.36) for $[Ni^{58}(LH)(L)]^+$ (100%), 345.05 (Calcd. 345.36) for $[Ni^{60}(LH)(L)]^+$ (41.87%), 283.01 (Calcd. 283.29) for $[Ni^{58}(LH)_2]^{+2}(THF)_2 + K^+$ (98.77%), 285.00 (Calcd. 285.29) for $[Ni^{60}(LH)_2]^{+2}(THF)_2 + K^+$ (48.13%), 199.98 (Calcd. 200.17) for $[Ni^{58}(L)]^+$ (66.87%), 201.99 (Calcd. 202.17) for $[Ni^{60}(L)]^+$ (29.38%); Λ_M (methanol) : 162.53 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ (1 : 2 electrolyte); μ_{eff}/μ_B : 2.91 at 300 K.

X-Ray structure determination :

Single crystals of **1** and **2** suitable for X-ray crystallography were carefully selected under a microscope and glued to a thin glass fiber. A good quality air stable single crystal of **1** with dimensions 0.3 × 0.2 × 0.2 mm and a single crystal of **2** with dimensions 0.3 × 0.4 × 0.3 mm were mounted on a Bruker Smart Apex II diffractometer equipped with 1K CCD instrument using a graphite monochromator with MoK_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Intensity data were collected at 298 K for **1** and at 293 K for **2** respectively. A total of 18602 reflections (unique reflections, 2504; $R_{int} = 0.0592$) were measured and 2504 data were observed [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] for the crystal of **1** and a total of 35960 reflections (unique reflections, 6070; $R_{int} = 0.0988$) were measured and 6070 data were observed [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] for the crystal of **2**. The crystals showed almost no decomposition under X-ray exposure during data collection. Cell parameters were determined by using SMART software¹³. Data reduction and corrections were performed using SAINTPLUS¹³ software. Absorption corrections were made via SADBAS¹⁴. The structure was solved by direct methods with the program SHELXS-97 and refined by full-matrix least-squares methods on all F^2 data with SHELXL-97¹⁴. All non-H atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms attached with C and N atoms were added theoretically and treated as riding on the concerned atoms. The final cycle of full-matrix least-squares refinement was based on observed

reflections and variable parameters. Data collection and structure refinement for the crystals of **1** and **2** are summarized in Table 1. Selected bond lengths, bond angles and hydrogen-bond geometries of **1** and **2** are listed in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. Check-cif results for **2** is appended in the supplementary section.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The synthetic scheme of **LH**, **1** and **2** is outlined in Fig. 1. Previously Otter and Hartshorn predicted that **LH** is susceptible to hydrolysis in polar solvents like methanol¹⁵. Accordingly earlier groups attempted its complexation only through *in situ* mode¹⁶. Here we have isolated it in the solid state through chromatographic separation.

(CH₃COO)](PF₆) (**1**). **1** is unique in the sense that it cannot be generated out of direct reaction of en and copper(II) acetate monohydrate even in dry THF. Our reactions in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 or even in 1 : 3 stoichiometric proportions of copper(II) acetate monohydrate and en invariably lead to violet [Cu(en)₃]²⁺.

Identical reaction of **LH** with nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate in 2 : 1 molar proportion in dry THF, followed by the addition of excess (1.5 molar proportion) NH₄PF₆ gives rise to brown block-shaped monomeric Ni^{II} compound, [Ni(LH)₂](PF₆)₂.(THF)₂ (**2**). **2** retains **LH** as such. The formation of **2** was established from its positive-ion ESI-MS peaks (Fig. 3).

The C, H and N micro analytical data of the crystals of **2** also corroborate the above formulation. The compound is two-electron paramagnetic.

Fig. 1. Scheme of synthesis of **LH**, **1** and **2**.

However, during its binding with Cu^{II} even under anhydrous THF medium, **LH** undergoes hydrolysis (Fig. 2) to yield novel one-electron paramagnetic, [Cu(en)₂

Fig. 2. Plausible mechanism of hydrolysis of **LH**.

FT-IR spectra :

For **1**, the sharp band of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the acetate group occurs at 1581 cm⁻¹ and the band at 1402 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ frequency. Here, $\Delta\nu = \nu_{\text{assy}} - \nu_{\text{symm}} = 179 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This is indicative of a monodentate acetate linkage¹⁷. The small but sharp band for C=N vibration of oxime¹⁸ in **2** is obtained at 1436 cm⁻¹ which is shifted to the lower wavenumber than that of **LH** (1471 cm⁻¹).

The sharp band for C=N vibration of Schiff base is discernable at 1598 cm⁻¹ which is also shifted to the lower wavenumber value from that of the free ligand (1609 cm⁻¹). These are only possible if N of C=N coordinates with a metal. So this is a signature¹⁹ that N of C=N coordinates with Ni⁺².

Fig. 3. ESI-MS spectrum of 2.

Crystal structure of $[Cu(en)_2(CH_3COO)](PF_6)$ (1) :

The copper center in 1 is nested in 'N₄O' donor sets (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. The X-ray structure of 1 at 30% probability.

In order to delve into the geometry around copper, we have taken recourse to estimate the trigonality index^{20–22} (τ). By definition, $\tau = (\alpha - \beta)/60$; where α and β respectively are the largest and the second largest angles around the central metal atom with the surrounded donors. A value of 0 for τ is a signature for a perfectly square pyramidal geometry; while it is of unity for a regular trigonal bipyramidal core. Taking, N1–Cu1–N3 = 170.9(3)° as α and N4–Cu1–N2 = 166.8(3)° as β , γ value in 1 comes out 0.068. Thus the geometry around copper is square pyramidal with little distortion. Crystal data and structure refinement for 1 is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for 1 and 2

CCDC No.	928577	999157
Color/shape	Blue/needle	Brown/block-shaped
Empirical formula	C ₆ H ₁₉ CuF ₆ N ₄ O ₂ P	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ NiF ₁₂ N ₆ O ₄ P ₂
Formula weight	387.76	779.25
Temperature (K)	298(2)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c	P2 ₁ /c
Unit cell dimensions		
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.4128(5)	8.7977(18)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.5199(5)	21.815(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	18.6388(9)	18.378(4)
β (°)	119.489(4)	100.82(3)
Volume (Å ³)	1453.83(13)	3464.4(12)
<i>Z</i>	4	4
ρ_{Calcd} (g/cm ³)	1.772	1.494
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	1.685	0.752
<i>F</i> (000)	788	1608
Crystal size (mm)	0.3 × 0.2 × 0.2	0.3 × 0.4 × 0.3
θ range for data collection (deg)	2.48 to 25.05	1.46 to 25.00
Limiting indices	-11 < <i>h</i> < 11, -11 < <i>k</i> < 11, -22 < <i>l</i> < 22	-10 < <i>h</i> < 10, -25 < <i>k</i> < 25, -21 < <i>l</i> < 21
Reflections collected/unique	18602/2504 [<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.0592]	35960/6070 [<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.0988]
Completeness to theta	97.2%	99.5%

Table-1 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

Data/restraints/ parameters	2504/72/237	6070/126/468
R_1 , all data, R_1 [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0830, 0.0991	0.1607, 0.2099
wR_2 , all data, wR_2 [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.2282, 0.2424	0.3939, 0.4959
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.167	1.655
Largest diff. peak and hole [$e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$]	1.702 and -0.846	3.129 and -0.946

The square-plane defined by the four nitrogen atoms of the two en moieties form two five-membered chelate rings. The apical position is occupied by the oxygen atom from acetate. The basal Cu–N distances are not the same and lie in the range from 1.992(7) to 2.032(7) Å. Cu–O distance, 2.331(6) Å, is quite large. It testifies tetragonal elongation of the square-pyramid. The F atoms have some disorder. The selected bond lengths and bond angles of **1** are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) for **1** and **2**

Cu1–N1	1.992(7)	N1–Cu1–N2	84.4(3)
Cu1–N2	2.018(7)	N4–Cu1–N3	83.5(3)
Cu1–N3	2.032(7)	N1–Cu1–N3	170.9(3)
Cu1–N4	1.999(7)	N1–Cu1–N4	97.1(3)
Cu1–O1	2.331(6)	N4–Cu1–N2	166.8(3)
O1–C5	1.234(11)	N2–Cu1–N3	92.9(3)
O2–C5	1.232(12)	N1–Cu1–O1	92.1(3)
N1–C1	1.447(12)	N4–Cu1–O1	92.1(3)
N2–C2	1.464(12)	N2–Cu1–O1	100.9(3)
N3–C3	1.440(12)	N3–Cu1–O1	96.9(3)
N4–C4	1.461(11)	C5–O1–Cu1	118.2(5)
C1–C2	1.551(16)	C1–N1–Cu1	110.6(6)
C3–C4	1.512(15)	C2–N2–Cu1	108.7(5)
C5–C6	1.511(13)	C3–N3–Cu1	107.8(5)
P1–F1A	1.56(3)	C4–N4–Cu1	110.3(6)
Ni1–N5	2.006(7)	N5–Ni1–N2	177.5(3)
Ni1–N2	2.022(8)	N5–Ni1–N1	105.4(3)
Ni1–N1	2.121(10)	N5–Ni1–N4	76.1(3)
Ni1–N4	2.124(8)	N2–Ni1–N4	106.0(3)
Ni1–N3	2.131(9)	N1–Ni1–N4	90.2(4)
Ni1–N6	2.144(9)	N5–Ni1–N3	97.4(3)
N5–C11	1.441(14)	N4–Ni1–N3	91.1(3)
N1–C1	1.295(14)	N5–Ni1–N6	81.4(3)
N6–C12	1.467(15)	N4–Ni1–N6	157.3(3)
N1–O1	1.364(12)	N3–Ni1–N6	95.2(4)

N2–C3	1.266(14)	N1–Ni1–N3	156.7(4)
N3–C6	1.383(16)	N2–Ni1–N1	76.2(4)
N4–C7	1.281(13)	O2–C5–C6	117.3(8)
N4–O2	1.377(11)	C7–N4–O2	112.7(8)
C1–C3	1.487(17)	N1–C1–C2	123.9(13)
C11–C12	1.511(16)	C1–C3–C4	121.2(11)
O3–C16	1.438(18)	N4–C7–C8	125.0(10)
O4–C18	1.419(18)	C8–C7–C9	121.3(9)
C18–C19	1.50(3)	N5–C9–C7	113.9(8)
O4–C17	1.417(17)	N6–C12–C11	111.0(9)
P1–F4	1.600(9)	F3–P1–F2	91.4(6)

There are some hydrogen bonds in **1** (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Open dash lines for H-bonding. F atoms are disordered. P–F bond : solid line for major part (52.4%), open line for minor part (47.6%).

The hydrogen bonds (Table 3) are between the hydrogen atoms attached with the nitrogen atoms, [N4–H4B, N4–H4A, N3–H3A, N2–H2B, N1–H1B, N1–H1A] of the ethylenediamine moieties and the oxygen atoms, [O1, O2] of acetate. These are : N4–H4B \cdots O2, N4–H4A \cdots O1, N3–H3A \cdots O2, N2–H2B \cdots O2, N1–H1B \cdots O1, N1–H1A \cdots O2. Hydrogen bonds are also there between the N atoms of N–H bonds and the F atoms of PF₆ anion. A packing diagram of the hydrogen bonded polymeric network is shown in Fig. 6.

Formulation of $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2](\text{PF}_6)_2 \cdot (\text{THF})_2$ (**2**) :

In spite of our repeated attempts, we could not harvest good quality single crystals of **2**. However, the poor diffraction data provides a fact of the structure – one $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2]^{2+}$ unit with two discrete hexafluorophosphate counter anions and two THF solvent molecules. Our C, H and N microanalyses, ESI-MS spectra, conductivity

Table 3. Hydrogen bonds (Å and °) for **1** and **2** (F atoms are disordered. A for major part and B for minor part)

D-H...A	<i>d</i> (D-H)	<i>d</i> (H...A)	<i>d</i> (D...A)	∠(D-H-A)	Symmetry code
For 1					
N4-H4B...F2B	0.90	2.59	3.26(2)	131.7	<i>x</i> -1, - <i>y</i> +3/2, <i>z</i> -1/2
N4-H4B...O2	0.90	2.37	2.986(10)	126.0	
N4-H4A...O1	0.90	2.23	3.032(10)	147.8	- <i>x</i> , <i>y</i> -1/2, - <i>z</i> +3/2
N3-H3B...F1B	0.90	2.35	3.133(18)	145.6	
N3-H3A...O2	0.90	2.22	3.009(10)	145.4	- <i>x</i> , <i>y</i> +1/2, - <i>z</i> +3/2
N2-H2B...O2	0.90	2.15	2.961(10)	150.1	- <i>x</i> , <i>y</i> +1/2, - <i>z</i> +3/2
N1-H1B...O1	0.90	2.14	2.983(9)	155.2	- <i>x</i> , <i>y</i> -1/2, - <i>z</i> +3/2
N1-H1A...O2	0.90	2.41	2.987(10)	122.2	
N1-H1A...F5A	0.90	2.36	3.15(3)	147.3	<i>x</i> -1, <i>y</i> , <i>z</i>
For 2					
O2-H2...O4	0.82	1.87	2.624(12)	152.3	
O1-H1...O3	0.82	1.83	2.642(14)	168.6	- <i>x</i> +1, <i>y</i> -1/2, - <i>z</i> +1/2
N6-H6B...F7	0.90	2.39	3.220(17)	154.2	
N6-H6B...F9A	0.90	2.39	3.18(3)	146.3	
N6-H6B...F9B	0.90	2.26	3.10(2)	154.6	
N6-H6A...F1	0.90	2.43	3.210(12)	145.5	
N6-H6A...F2	0.90	2.34	3.183(14)	155.2	
N3-H3B...F5	0.90	2.37	3.234(13)	160.9	- <i>x</i> +2, - <i>y</i> , - <i>z</i> +1
N3-H3B...F4	0.90	2.39	3.165(12)	144.0	- <i>x</i> +2, - <i>y</i> , - <i>z</i> +1
N3-H3A...F2	0.90	2.48	3.277(13)	147.5	

Fig. 6. The packing diagram of **1**. H atoms without H bond and minor of disordered F atoms bond are omitted. Cu : light cyan, O : red, N : blue, C : grey, H : light green open cycle, P : magenta, F : light green.

and thermogravimetric study of **2** also corroborate the above formulation. **2** bears a 'NiN₆' core. Here two oximato nitrogens, two imine nitrogens and two amine nitrogens from two ligands (**LH**) complete the donor sets around the nickel center.

The structure consists of one [Ni(LH)₂]²⁺ cation to-

gether with two discrete hexafluorophosphate counter anions. The Ni1-N2 (imine) and Ni1-N5 (imine) bond distances are of 2.022(8) and 2.006(7) Å respectively. The amine N bonds, Ni1-N3 [2.131(9) Å] and Ni1-N6 [2.144(9) Å] are comparatively longer than the imine N bonds. The bond distances of Ni1-N1 (oximato) and Ni1-

Fig. 7. ORTEP view of the compound, **2**; ellipsoids at 30% probability.

N4 (oximato) are of 2.121(10) and 2.124(8) Å respectively. Since the bond lengths are different, the adopted molecular geometry is not perfectly octahedral. It is somewhat pentagonal pyramidal. Here the five N atoms form the basal plane of the pentagon. However, the pentagon is not regular. The $\angle N5-Ni1-N4$ [76.1(3)°] and $\angle N2-Ni1-N1$ [76.2(4)°] are of the same order. The other two angles $\angle N1-Ni1-N4$ [90.2(4)°] and $\angle N5-Ni1-N2$ [177.5(3)°] are not close to each other. Here all the angles are greater than 72°. For regular pentagon the angles must be 72°. It is interesting to note that the P-F bonds in the anionic part PF_6^{-1} are not the same and are in the range of 1.527(10) to 1.63(3) Å. There are some hydrogen bonds in the complex. These bonds (Table 3) are between the hydrogen atoms attached with nitrogen [N6-H6B, N6-H6A, N3-H3B, N3-H3A] of ethylenediamine side of the ligand, **LH** and the F atoms of PF_6 anion. Hydrogen bonds are also there between the oxygen atoms [O1, O2] of oxime ligand and oxygen atoms [O3, O4] of solvent THF. These are: O2-H2...O4 and O1-H1...O3. Thus the two dangling -OH groups of complex **2** stabilize the crystal structure via hydrogen bond interactions between the ligands and solvent THFs.

Redox behavior :

The redox behaviors of **1** and **2** have been studied by cyclic voltammetry (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9) in DMF at GC working electrode under N_2 atmosphere. **1** shows an irreversible cathodic wave (couple-I) with a peak potential

Fig. 8. CV of **1** ($1.03 \times 10^{-3} M$) in DMF at a scan rate of 200 $mV s^{-1}$.

Fig. 9. CV of **2** ($1.001 \times 10^{-3} M$) in DMF at a scan rate of 100 $mV s^{-1}$.

(E_{pc}) of -0.404 V vs Ag/AgCl. The associated peak current, i_{pc} is $3.30 \mu\text{A}$. **2** exhibits one cathodic wave (couple-I) at E_{pc} of -0.573 V vs Ag/AgCl with i_{pc} of $5.44 \mu\text{A}$. **LH** is electrochemically inert in our experimental potential window. Thus the reductions are metal centered. Comparison of the voltammetric peak currents with those of ferrocene-ferrocenium couple (0.44 V vs Ag/AgCl) under the same experimental condition establishes that each of the reductive responses in **1** and **2** involve one electron⁵. Consequently, the couples are assigned as : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ for **1** and $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{I}}$ for **2**.

Thermal analyses :

The thermal behaviors (TGA and DTA) of **1** and **2** have been studied (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11) within the temperature range 33.0 – 810.0 °C and 32.0 – 800.0 °C respectively in a dynamic N_2 atmosphere (flow rate = 20.0

mL/min). 1.751 mg of **1** was heated in a platinum crucible at a heating rate of 12.0 °C per minute and 6.063 mg of **2** was heated in a platinum crucible at a heating rate of 15.0 °C per minute. Dried and purified $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ powder was used as a reference in each case.

The thermal losses (theoretical and experimental) with the corresponding assigned fragments are tabulated in Table 4. These assignments correlate well with the literature^{23–25}.

BVS calculation :

The oxidation states of ‘+2’ for copper and nickel in **1** and **2** respectively have been reproduced from Bond Valence Sum (BVS) model^{26,27}. This semi-empirical model correlates the oxidation state of a central metal ion to the bond lengths of all the bonds surrounding it. In this method,

Fig. 10. TGA-DTA of **1**.

Fig. 11. TGA-DTA of **2**.

Table 4. Thermal analyses of **1** and **2**

Compd.	Temp. range (°C)	Theo. (%)	Expt. (%)	Mass loss	Heat loss	DTA peak (°C)
1	33.0–142.3	–	–	thermally stable	–	–
	142.3–238.4	15.22	14.61	removal of bonded acetate group ligand	endothermic	238.4
	238.4–282.6	30.95	30.76	combustion two ethylenediamine molecule	endothermic	288.9
	282.6–295	37.69	37.14	removal of PF ₆	– large	–
	295–800	16.14	15.71	elemental copper	exothermic	–
2	32.0–45.6	–	–	thermally stable	–	–
	45.6–200	18.50	18.18	removal of two THF molecules	exothermic	191.2
	200–338.6	37.47	35.91	removal of two PF ₆ molecules	exothermic	243.8
	338.6–800	44.03	45.91	ligand and the metallic nickel combustion	large exothermic	–

the valence V_{ij} of a bond between two atoms i and j is given by an exponential equation (1), where r_{ij} is the length of the bond (expressed in Å) and r_0 , a parameter characteristic of the bond.

$$V_{ij} = \exp [(r_0 - r_{ij})/0.37] \quad (1)$$

The bond valence parameter r_0 , have the unit in Å. The oxidation number V_i of a atom(i) is a simple algebraic sum of the V_{ij} values of all the bonds(n) around the atom(i) following equation (2).

$$V_i = \sum_{i=1}^n V_{ij} \quad (2)$$

This V_i is also known as BVS of the atom, i . Thus, for a particular bond type if r_0 is known, BVS can be evaluated knowing the crystallographic r_{ij} values. Taking the r_0 values for Cu⁺²-N, Cu⁺²-O and Ni⁺²-N bonds of 1.719, 1.679 and 1.673 Å respectively²⁸, the BVS for copper and nickel in **1** and **2** come out 1.994 and 1.959 valence units (vu). The calculations are listed in Table 5.

Our calculated BVS corresponds quite satisfactorily with the error limit of ± 0.250 vu as proposed by Thorp^{29,30}.

Table 5. Bond valence values for central copper in **1**

Compds.	Bond type	Bond lengths (Å)	$S_{ij} = \exp [(r_0 - r_{ij})/0.37]$	BVS for copper center
1	Cu1–N1	1.992	0.478	1.994
	Cu1–N2	1.999	0.469	
	Cu1–N3	2.018	0.446	
	Cu1–N4	2.032	0.429	
	Cu1–O1	2.331	0.172	
2	Ni1–N1	2.121	0.298	1.959
	Ni1–N2	2.022	0.389	
	Ni1–N3	2.131	0.290	
	Ni1–N4	2.124	0.295	
	Ni1–N5	2.006	0.406	
	Ni1–N6	2.144	0.280	

Conclusions

Here we have been able to isolate and characterize a hydrolysis-prone Schiff base ligand, 3-(2-aminoethylimino)-butan-2-one oxime (**LH**). During complexation with copper(II) acetate monohydrate, **LH** hydrolyses to produce novel [Cu(en)₂(CH₃COO)](PF₆) (**1**) in presence of PF₆⁻¹ counter anion; but under identical situation, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate reacts with native **LH** enabling us to isolate, [Ni(LH)₂](PF₆)₂·(THF)₂ (**2**). **1** and

2 have been characterized through available physical, spectroscopic and analytical means. Additionally, the X-ray crystal structure of **1** has been determined. The X-ray structure of **2** also supports the formulation of **2**. In DMF, the redox studies of **1** and **2** respectively show Cu^{II}/Cu^I and Ni^{II}/Ni^I reduction couples. Thermal analyses of **1** and **2** are fully consistent with our proposed formulations. BVS calculations reproduce the oxidation state of copper and nickel in **1** and **2** satisfactorily.

Supplementary material

CCDC 928577 and 999157 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for **1** and **2** respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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